

An improved method of synthesis of precursors for amino-Claisen rearrangement

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Abstract : *N*-Allylarylamines are useful precursors in amino-Claisen rearrangements affording 2-allylarylamines in one step. An improved method for the synthesis of a series of *N*-allylarylamines (2a-h) has been described.

Keywords : Heterocycles, amino-Claisen rearrangement.

Amino-Claisen rearrangement of *N*-allylarylamines (2) provides a one-pot synthetic entry to the 2-allylarylamines (3)¹. 2-Allylarylamines are important precursors in indole and quinoline synthesis through the process of palladium assisted heteroannulations^{2,3}. Coupled with this, 2-allylarylamines have been shown to involve a unique photochemistry, in stereoselective synthesis of 2-indanols⁴ and this has stimulated further interest in this molecule from yet another perspective.

We required a good method for the preparation of *N*-allylarylamines (2) for our studies on the synthesis of indoles. The *N*-allylarylamines result from direct allylation of arylamine by allylhalides⁵, by reaction of allylamine and arylhalides⁶ or by allylboration of nitro compounds⁷. The procedure of direct base promoted allylation of arylamine by allyl halides is by far the most simplest⁵. Various base-solvent combinations viz. Na sand-toluene⁸, NaHCO₃-water⁹, K₂CO₃-acetone¹⁰ have been used in the reaction to enhance the yield of the product. The reaction under these conditions, have been shown to form a complex mixture of bis-*N*-allylated product with mono-*N*-allylated product, from which, mono-*N*-allylated products are very difficult to separate. We describe in this note an improved method of direct base promoted allylation of arylamine (1) which selectively gives mono-*N*-allylarylamines (2) in good yields (Scheme 1).

The method involved, stirring of a mixture of arylamine (1a-h, 1.0 equiv), anhydrous K₂CO₃ (1.0 equiv), allyl bromide (1.1 equiv) in DMF at room temperature for 12–16 h. The usual workup of the mixture furnished 2a-h in good yields 67–84% (Table 1). It seems likely that

Scheme 1

K₂CO₃ in DMF acted as a strong non-nucleophilic base¹¹ and prevented the formation of the protonated species of parent arylamine, with the acid released in the reaction.

The procedure described, circumvented the need of cumbersome purification process as the *N*-allylarylamine (2) was obtained exclusively the sole organic product as indicated by ¹H NMR. As the reaction occurred at room temperature without heating the formation of bis-*N*-allylated product was suppressed. However, there is a limitation in this method with regard to longer duration of reaction which it required, compared to other reported methods.

All the products 2a-h were characterized by elemental and spectral analysis (IR, ¹H NMR), and by comparison of the data with authentic samples 2a-b, 2e-h prepared through known routes^{5,12,13}. IR spectra of all the compounds showed the characteristic absorptions for NH-group around 3570–3459 cm⁻¹ and vinylic group at 990 and 920 cm⁻¹. The ¹H NMR spectra of 2a-h showed signals for N-CH₂- protons at δ 3.67–3.90, vinylic protons around at δ 5.00–6.10 and NH- proton in 2c and 2d around δ 8.12 and in others around δ 3.50 (which exchanged with D₂O). The IR and ¹H NMR data corroborated fully to the formation of the compounds 2a-h.

Table 1. Physical and spectroscopic data of the *N*-allylarylamines (2a-h)

Product ^a	Yield (%)	IR (cm ⁻¹)	¹ H NMR (δ, ppm)
ArNHCH ₂ CH=CH ₂ 2a, Ar = 2-CH ₃ Ph	84	3442, 2933, 2852, 1665, 1605, 1490, 1465, 990, 918, 743	7 20-6 40 (4H, m, ArH), 6 08-5 70 (1H, m, -CH=), 5 38-5 00 (2H, m, =CH ₂), 3 67 (2H, d <i>J</i> 5 5 Hz, -CH ₂ -), 3 40 (1H, br s, NH), 2 10 (3H, s, CH ₃)
2b, Ar = 2-OCH ₃ Ph	80	3459, 2937, 2834, 1643, 1601, 1512, 1457, 995, 919, 738	7 00-6 60 (4H, m, ArH), 6 10-5 92 (1H, m, -CH=), 5 30-5 16 (2H, m, =CH ₂), 4 40 (1H, br s, NH), 3 87 (2H, m, -CH ₂ -), 3 80 (3H, s, OCH ₃)
2c, Ar = 2-CONH ₂ Ph	72	3360, 2840, 1660, 1630, 1600, 1447, 992, 920, 747	8 12 (1H, br s, NH), 7 60 (1H, dd, <i>J</i> 1 7, 8 0 Hz, ArH), 7 33-7 25 (1H, m, ArH), 6 67 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 8 2 Hz, ArH), 6 60 (1H, t, <i>J</i> 8 0 Hz, ArH), 6 10-5 90 (3H, m, -CH=, CONH ₂), 5 31-5 14 (2H, m, =CH ₂), 3 86 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 6 2 Hz, -CH ₂ -)
2d, Ar = 2-COOEtPh	67	3370, 2951, 2845, 1690, 1616, 1590, 1518, 1455, 994, 920, 751	7 91 (1H, dd, <i>J</i> 1 6, 8 2 Hz, ArH), 7 82 (1H, br s, NH), 7 38-7 32 (1H, m, ArH), 6 65-6 52 (2H, m, ArH), 6 03-5 90 (1H, m, -CH=), 5 34-5 14 (2H, m, =CH ₂), 4 30 (2H, q, <i>J</i> 8 0 Hz, CH ₂ CH ₃), 3 85 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 5 1 Hz, -CH ₂ -), 1 40 (3H, t, <i>J</i> 8 0 Hz, CH ₂ CH ₃)
2e, Ar = 2-NH ₂ Ph	77	3390, 2940, 2860, 1629, 1588, 1511, 1448, 992, 918, 745	6 90-6 84 (1H, m, ArH), 6 79-6 64 (3H, m, ArH), 6 10-5 98 (1H, m, -CH=), 5 31-5 18 (2H, m, =CH ₂), 3 80-3 76 (2H, dd, <i>J</i> 1 6, 5 5 Hz, -CH ₂ -), 3 46 (3H, br s, NH, NH ₂)
2f, Ar = 3-ClPh	79	3437, 2920, 2848, 1665, 1600, 1510 1442, 982, 920, 795, 710	7 10-6 47 (4H, m, ArH), 6 90-5 92 (1H, m, -CH=), 5 31-5 13 (2H, m, =CH ₂), 3 90 (1H, s, NH), 3 76 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 6 1 Hz, -CH ₂ -)
2g, Ar = 4-ClPh	84	3422, 2928, 2870, 1670, 1599, 1486, 1465, 998, 921, 820	7 12 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 9 Hz, ArH), 6 65 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 9 Hz, ArH), 6 10-5 89 (1H, m, -CH=), 5 30-5 18 (2H, m, =CH ₂), 3 98 (1H, s, NH), 3 80 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 6 2 Hz, -CH ₂ -)
2h, Ar = 1-Naphthyl	82	3437, 3055, 2980, 2847, 1590, 1485, 1446, 994, 920	7 74-6 58 (7H, m, ArH), 6 06-5 90 (1H, m, -CH=), 5 31-5 17 (2H, m, =CH ₂), 4 12 (1H, s, NH), 3 82 (d, <i>J</i> 5 2 Hz, -CH ₂ -)

^aProducts were fully characterized by elemental analysis, IR and ¹H NMR spectral data

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on Pye Unicam model SP3-300 infracord in neat and on KBr pellets. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on Varian EM 360 L using CDCl₃ and DMSO-*d*₆ as solvent and TMS as an internal reference.

General procedure for the preparation of N-allylarylamines (2a-h) :

To a solution of arylamines (1a-h, 0.0364 mol) in DMF (80 ml) was added K₂CO₃ (5.03 g, 0.0364 mol) with stirring. To this solution, allyl bromide (4.83 g, 0.040 mol) was dropwise added. The resulting mixture was stirred at room temperature for 12–16 h. After the completion of the reaction (checked by TLC), the reac-

tion mixture was poured into water, extracted with Et₂O (5 × 100 ml), dried over anhydrous MgSO₄ and concentrated. The residue was purified by column chromatography on silica gel using hexane-ethyl acetate (10 : 1, v/v) to give *N*-allylarylamines (2a-h) as oils (yields 67–84%, Table 1) excepting 2c, which was obtained as white solid m.p 145 °C

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